

Upper Gastrointestinal Lesions- A Comprehensive Insight to the Analogy of Endoscopic and Histopathological Findings

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Abstract:

Background: While an Endoscopy provides a unique opportunity to visualize the mucosal surface of the gastrointestinal tract, the histopathology of the biopsy sample by an experienced pathologist is vital to correct the disorders of the alimentary tract. Our study aims to determine the histopathological spectrum of the gastrointestinal tract lesions and to correlate the endoscopic diagnosis and histopathological diagnosis.

Methods: It is a retrospective observational study done in the Department of Pathology at SIMS and RC, on all upper gastrointestinal (GI) biopsies for duration of one year May 2022 to May 2023. Inadequate specimens, superficial biopsies, hemorrhagic tissue samples, and fibro collagenous tissue observed on the biopsy segments were excluded from the study. In a semi-structured proforma, the demographic details, endoscopic findings, and histopathological findings in upper gastrointestinal biopsies. The data was entered into a Microsoft Excel spreadsheet and was analyzed using SPSS v26.0.

Results: The study included a total of 120 study participants who underwent upper gastrointestinal endoscopy. There were 64 male and 54 female patients with a male: female ratio of 1.14:1. The most common sites from which the lesion was observed, and biopsy was sought were in the stomach 44 cases (Body of stomach, Antrum, Fundus, and Pylorus) 36 cases (40%) were neoplastic, 84 cases (60%) were non-neoplastic. Among the non-neoplastic lesions, most were of chronic non-specific gastritis, ulcers, and polyps, and among neoplastic lesions squamous cell carcinoma and adenocarcinoma were commonly observed. The sensitivity and specificity of histopathology when compared to endoscopic findings, was observed to be 96.34% and 83.89% respectively.

Conclusion: Endoscopic biopsy is an initial investigation of choice in patients with upper GI symptoms which permits exact diagnosis along with providing an opportunity to see the lesion status and helps in deciding specific therapy. The histopathological study helps to detect mucosal lesions at an early stage like atrophy, intestinal metaplasia, and dysplasia to prevent their progression into invasive cancers; hence histopathology remains the gold standard for the diagnosis.

Keywords: Endoscopic Biopsy; Chronic Gastritis; Squamous Cell Carcinoma; GIST.

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Introduction

Human gastro-intestinal tract is long, tortuous, and a common site for lesions like congenital, inflammatory and neoplastic in origin. They are most commonly encountered in clinical practice worldwide. [1] Upper gastrointestinal tracts include oral cavity, oesophagus, stomach and duodenum where the minimally invasive procedures are done such as endoscopy, which is safe and well tolerated. [2] Upper GI Endoscopy is done for evaluating both benign and malignant conditions such as dyspepsia, odynophagia, gastroesophageal reflux disease (GERD), Barrett's esophagus,

dysplasia, peptic ulcer disease (PUD), oesophageal and gastric carcinoma. This is more important now than ever, since gastric carcinoma prevails as the 4th most common cause of cancer-related mortality worldwide. While an Endoscopy provides a unique opportunity to visualize the mucosal surface of gastro-intestinal tract, the histopathological examination of the biopsy sample by an experienced pathologist is vital to provide correct diagnosis to cure the disorders of the alimentary tract. [3,4] Endoscopic biopsies are performed not only as a diagnostic modality and

gold standard investigation used in practice for evaluation of a disease but also for monitoring the course, determining its extent, response to therapy and early detection of complications. [3,4]

Our study aims to determine the histopathological spectrum of the gastrointestinal tract lesions and to correlate the endoscopic biopsies and diagnosis with the histopathological diagnosis along with distribution of various alimentary tract lesions according to age and sex, which further helps the clinician to diagnose and to upgrade the plan the management of the disease.

Objectives:

1. To determine the spectrum of histopathological findings in upper gastrointestinal endoscopic biopsies.
2. To compare age and sex distribution of various upper gastrointestinal biopsies.
3. To correlate endoscopic and histopathology findings.

Inclusion Criteria: All upper gastro-intestinal (UGI) biopsy slides were reviewed.

Exclusion Criteria: Inadequate specimens, superficial biopsies, hemorrhagic tissue samples, and fibro collagenous tissue observed on the biopsy segments were excluded from the study.

Methods and Materials

It is a retrospective observational study done in the Department of Pathology at Sapthagiri Institute of Medical Science and Research Centre, on all upper gastro-intestinal (UGI) biopsies for duration of one year May2022 to May 2023.

A total of 120 samples were found to fit the inclusion criteria. A copy of the endoscopic report, mentioning the site of the biopsy, a macroscopic description of the lesion if possible, and the

essential clinical information such as age, immune status, duration of symptoms, and treatment if any were acquired before assessment. All the biopsy samples were fixed in 10% buffered formalin, followed by tissue processing by an automated tissue processor, cut at 3-4-micron thick sections, and stained with Haematoxylin and Eosin. Giemsa stain was used for H. Pylori. All tumors were classified according to the WHO classification system (2019). In a semi-structured proforma, the demographic details, endoscopic findings, and histopathological findings in upper gastro-intestinal biopsies were collected.

The data was entered into a Microsoft Excel spreadsheet and was analyzed using SPSS v 26.0. The appropriate tests were used to correlate the age and sex distribution of lesions occurring in the gastrointestinal tract, endoscopically and histologically. Correlation of age, sex, endoscopic, and histopathology findings were performed using Pearson's correlation. Any p-value $p = < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

Results

The current study included a total of 120 study participants who underwent upper gastrointestinal endoscopy. The study assessed endoscopic biopsies in the light of primarily ruling out inflammatory, premalignant, and malignant processes.

Endoscopic biopsy site wise distribution with histopathological findings: Out of 120 endoscopic biopsies received from the medical gastroenterology department, 84 cases (60%) were Non-neoplastic lesions and 36 cases (40%) were malignant lesions. The distribution of lesions is depicted in the pie chart (based on the anatomical site)[Fig 1]. Also, the lesions are distributed based on the anatomical site as benign and malignant [Table 1].

Figure 1: Pie chart representing the number of endoscopic biopsies based on the anatomical site

Table1: Site wise distribution of benign and malignant lesions based on Anatomical structure.

Sl no	Site of lesion	Non-neoplastic lesions	Malignant lesions
01	Oesophagus (No of cases=44,M=25,F=19)	26	18
02	GE junction (No of cases=05,M=03,F=02)	02	03
03	Stomach:		
(i)	Fundus (No of cases=09,M=04,F=05)	08	01
(ii)	Body of stomach (No of cases=29,M=15,F=14)	23	06
(iii)	Antrum (No of cases=08,M=04,F=04)	06	02
(iv)	Pyloric region (No of cases=01,M=01,F=00)	01	00
04	Duodenum (No of cases=22,M=12,F=10)	18	04
05	Pyriiform fossa (No of cases=02,M=00,F=02)	00	02
Total cases =26 cases		84	36

* M- Male, F- Female.

Distribution of cases based on age and gender:

Out of 120 cases, the highest number of biopsies was observed in patients between 41 to 60 years (44.2%) followed by 61-80 years (33.3%) and 21-40 years (16.7%). Out of 120 patients, 64 cases (53.3%) were males and 56 cases (46.7%) were

females. The male-to-female ratio is 1.14 :1. The mean age of the study population was 54.4 +/- 12.91 years, which was much higher than the majority of the prevalence studies available in such a population. The youngest patient was 5 years old and the oldest patient was 90 years old.

Table 2: Distribution of cases based on age and gender

Sl no	Age groups	Males	Females	Total cases (n=120)
01	< 20 years	1	2	3(2.5%)
02	21-40 years	11	9	20(16.7%)
03	41-60 years	29	24	53(44.2%)
04	61-80 years	21	19	40(33.3%)
05	> 80 years	2	2	4(3.3%)
Total cases		64	56	26

Table 3: Correlation of endoscopic and histopathological findings of benign esophageal lesions:

Endoscopic findings	Histopathological findings						
	Esophagitis	Barret's esophagus	HPV Induced viral oesophagitis	Hyperplastic polyp	Reflux esophagitis	Bullous disorder	Negative for malignancy
Esophagitis	6	-	1	-	-	-	-
Ulcer	2	-	-	-	-	1	3
Barret's esophagus	-	3	-	1	-	-	-
Candidiasis	-	-	-	1	1	-	-
Stricture	1	-	-	-	-	-	-
Reflux esophagitis	1	-	-	-	2	-	-
Polyp	3	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total=26	13	3	1	2	3	1	3

Out of the 44 cases of esophageal biopsies, 26 cases (59.1%) were concluded as non-neoplastic and 18 cases (40.9%) emerged as neoplastic. Among the non-neoplastic lesions, 13 cases were of esophagitis, 03 cases of each with Barret's esophagus and reflux esophagitis, 02 cases of the hyperplastic polyp, and a single case of each

bullous disorder and HPV esophagitis in a 30-year-old male, with grossly punched out shallow ulcers were diagnosed, showing viral cytopathic changes of the stromal and endothelial cells. Even though, three lesions were suspicious for malignancy with ulcerative lesions on endoscopy, were negative for malignancy.

Table 4: Correlation between endoscopic and histopathological findings of benign stomach lesions: (A) Gastro-Esophageal junction

Endoscopic findings	Histopathological findings	
	Chronic non-specific inflammation	Hyperplastic polyp
GE junction nodule	01	-
GE junction polyp	-	01

Table 4(B): Fundus of stomach:

Endoscopic findings	Histopathological findings	
	Fundic gland polyp	Chronic active gastritis with H.pylori infection
Polyp	04	-
Gastric nodule	03	01
Total=08	07	01

Table 4(C): Body of stomach:

Endoscopic findings	Histopathological findings						
	Hyperplastic polyp	Chronic gastritis with Hpylori infection	Atrophic gastritis	Xanthoma	Erosive gastritis	dysplasia	Negative for malignancy
Polyp	01	-	-	-	-	01	-
Gastric nodularity	01	04	-	-	-	-	-
Atrophic gastritis	-	03	01	-	-	-	01
erosions	-	03	-	-	01	-	-
Gastric ulcer	-	03	-	-	-	-	01
Normal study	-	02	-	-	-	-	-
Xanthoma	-	-	-	01	-	-	-
Total=23	02	15	01	01	01	01	02

Table 4(D): Antrum and pylorus of stomach

Endoscopic findings	Histopathological findings			
	Inflammatory polyp	Active gastritis	Chronic gastritis with H.Pylori infection	Hyperplastic polyp
Antral ulcer	-	01	02	-
Antral erosion	01	01	01	-
Pyloric polyp	-	-	-	01
Total =7	01	02	03	01

Among the 52 cases from the Stomach, 40 cases were non-neoplastic and 12 cases turned out to be malignancy. Among the non-neoplastic lesions, chronic gastritis with H.Pylori infection was most commonly found among all sites of stomach biopsies followed by hyperplastic polyp.

Table 5: Correlation between endoscopic and histopathological findings of duodenal lesions:

Endoscopic findings	Histopathological findings			
	Chronic nonspecific inflammation	Adenoma	Chronic active duodenitis	Negative for malignancy
Normal study	03	-	-	-
Growth	02	-	-	02
Erosions	01	-	01	-
Nodule	03	-	01	-
Polyp	-	02	01	-
NET	01	-	-	-
Duodenal lymphangectasia	01	-	-	-
Total cases = 18	11	02	03	02

Out of the 22 cases of duodenal biopsies 18 were non-neoplastic and 04 malignant lesions. Of these lesions, 11 cases depicted Chronic non-specific inflammation, 03 cases of Chronic active duodenitis, and 02 cases of adenoma were identified. Even though, 02 lesions were suspicious for malignancy with ulcerative growth on endoscopy, were negative for malignancy.

Table 6: Endoscopic and Histopathology correlation of Neoplastic lesions with ulcero- proliferative growth on endoscopic findings:

Site of lesion	Histopathology diagnosis	Total no of cases
Esophagus	Squamous cell carcinoma=15 Adenocarcinoma=3	18 (50%)
GE Junction	Squamous cell carcinoma=01 Adenocarcinoma=02	03 (8.3%)
Fundus of stomach	Adenocarcinoma=01	01 (2.78%)
Body of stomach	GIST=01 Adenocarcinoma=05	06 (16.7%)
Antrum of stomach	Adenocarcinoma=02	02 (5.56%)
Pylorus of stomach	Nil	Nil
Duodenum	Adenocarcinoma=02 Neuroendocrine tumour=02	04 (11.1%)
Cricopharynx and pyriform fossa.	Squamous cell carcinoma=02	02 (5.56%)
Total cases = 36	SCC= 18, ADENOCARCINOMA=15 ,GIST=01, NET=02	26(100%)

In the present study out of 120 cases, 36(40%) cases are proved to be malignant. A total of 18 cases (50%) of Squamous cell carcinoma, 15 cases (41.7%) of Adenocarcinoma, 02 cases (5.56%) of Neuroendocrine tumors and 01 cases (2.78%) of GIST were seen among malignant lesions. Most of the patients presented clinically were suspicious of

malignancy as most of them had exophytic or ulcerative growth in the endoscopy. Other two features nodularity with thickened mucosa with loss of rugal folds detected by magnified endoscopy also raised the suspicion of gastric malignancy.

Table 7: Overall correlation of Endoscopic Diagnosis with Histopathological Diagnosis

Final histopathological diagnosis	Endoscopic findings	Percentage (%)
Correlated	99	82.5%
Not correlated	21	17.5%
Total no of cases	26	100%

Out of 120 cases the endoscopic diagnosis was compared with histopathological diagnosis; Out of which 99 cases (82.5%) correlated with final histopathological diagnosis ($p < 0.05$).

Discussion:

Upper gastrointestinal symptoms like dyspepsia, vomiting, abdominal pain, ulcers, etc. are very common causes of discomfort amongst patients & are the common reasons for referral for endoscopic examination. The modern endoscope has evolved from a rigid hollow metal tube to a light, flexible fiberoptic system using self-illumination. It not only allows visual inspection of the GI tract but also permits access to suspected tissue areas with the aid of a biopsy needle. Endoscopic biopsy and subsequent histopathological study stand as one of the best diagnostic modalities in making diagnosis of GIT lesions – Neoplastic and Non-neoplastic. The aim of the present study is also to demonstrate the same importance with precise statistical study. We have attempted to compare our data with other established studies in the literature.

The study was conducted from May 2022 to May 2023 and comprised 120 upper gastrointestinal endoscopic biopsies, of which 47cases (39.20%) were gastric, 44 cases (36.70%) were esophageal

biopsies, 22(18.30%) cases were duodenal biopsies, 05 cases (4.17%) from GE junction and 02 cases (1.67%) from pyriform fossa. In the present study most common site for upper gastrointestinal endoscopic biopsy is the stomach, followed by esophagus and duodenum which was similar to the studies done by Maiti et al., Jaffary et al., and Alghamdi et al. [5,6,7].

Age and sex distribution:

Out of 120 patients, with neoplastic and non-neoplastic endoscopic biopsies, males have predominantly affected i.e. 64 cases (53.30%) while the rest were from females 54 cases (46.70%). This was also proved by another study done by ShennakMM et al. [8] The male: female ratio was 1.14:1. The ratio is suggestive of male predominance, mostly because of increased exposure of males to more risk factors, same established by the study done by JC Paymaster et al. [9]

In the present study, the highest incidence of upper gastrointestinal endoscopic lesions is seen between 41-60 years which comprises 44.60% of the total number of biopsies, similar to the study conducted by Qureshi et al. [10] with 72 endoscopic biopsy samples over 2 years. In line with studies by

Chukwurah et al. [11] ours revealed an incidence of most lesions in the fourth and fifth decades. In the present study, the oldest patient was 90 years old and the youngest was 5 years old. The age-related difference could be due to the variations in risk factors among the different age groups. The incidence of neoplastic lesions was common in the 5th decade with male predominance. Among the neoplastic lesions, the esophagus was the most common site followed by the stomach.

Oesophageal biopsies:

Among the 44 esophageal biopsies, in non-neoplastic lesions, 26 cases (59.1%) were more common than in neoplastic lesions 18 cases (40.9%). The majority of cases were inflammatory or benign in nature and chronic non-specific inflammation (34.6%) was the commonest diagnosis. These findings are in comparison with the findings of studies conducted by Krishnappa Rashmi et al. [2] and Jonnalagadda K, Karre S et al. [13] Hirachand et al. [14] which also showed that the non-neoplastic lesions outnumbered the neoplastic lesions. Most of the malignant lesions were attributed to the esophagus, of which 15 cases (83.3%) were from Squamous cell carcinoma and 03 cases (16.7%) from Adenocarcinoma. The commonly encountered lesion in the esophagus was squamous cell carcinoma which is similar to the study done by Abhilash et al. [15]

Among squamous cell carcinoma of the esophagus, the most common was moderately differentiated

carcinoma (83.1%) followed by well differentiated (11.6%) and poorly differentiated carcinoma (5.10%). In the present study, most of the patients with esophageal cancer were seen in the 6th and 7th decades. The distensibility of the esophagus and the lack of serosa may be to blame for the general late age at which esophageal cancer symptoms manifest, delaying symptoms until the tumor has progressed. Additionally, due to a lack of knowledge and accessibility to medical facilities, the majority of patients in our community receive their diagnosis later in life. The majority of people (55.60%) affected by esophageal cancers were female. The female preponderance may be explained by the fact that the majority of established risk factors for esophageal cancer are linked to behaviors like tobacco chewing, which is known to be more common among women than men in the community under study.

In Western countries, the frequency of adenocarcinoma is presently on the rise. Recent studies also indicate an increasing tendency in the occurrence of adenocarcinoma throughout our country, perhaps because of altering lifestyle choices among the Indian population, such as increased smoking and alcohol usage. This observation was confirmed by Krishnappa R et al. [12] Bukhari U et al. [16] which showed a high incidence of neoplastic lesions when compared to the non-neoplastic lesions.

Figure 2: Barrets Oesophagus; A: Endoscopic biopsy of lower esophagus depicts the salmon coloured mucosa between pale squamous mucosa. B: Microscopy shows the transition from stratified squamous epithelium to tall columnar mucinous epithelium (H & E; Low power view x100)

Figure 3: Squamous Cell Carcinoma Esophagus; A: Endoscopic biopsy of middle one third of esophagus with an ulceroproductive growth. B: Microscopy shows an infiltrating Squamous cell carcinoma with polygonal tumor cells, pleomorphic hyperchromatic nuclei, abundant eosinophilic cytoplasm(H & E; Low power view x100)

Gastric Biopsies:

Out of 47 cases of gastric biopsies, we had there were biopsies from fundus (09 cases), body (29 cases), antrum (08 cases), and pyloric region (01 cases) respectively. Out of 47 cases, 38 cases (80.9%) were non-neoplastic and 9 cases (19.1%) were neoplastic respectively, this observation correlated well with a study done by Venkatesh V et al.¹⁷ revealed, that out of the total 103 biopsies from the stomach, 91 cases (88.34%) were non-neoplastic and 12 cases (11.65%) were neoplastic.

Chronic nonspecific gastritis was the most frequent histological diagnosis among these gastric non-neoplastic lesions which presented as gastric nodules, polyps, and erosions endoscopically, which is similar to the study done by Hirachand et al. [14] (35.16%) and Anjana ML et al.¹⁸ (52.8%). The present study had a low incidence of H Pylori chronic gastritis (6.25%), which is in contrast with a study done by Sharma et al. [26] where H. pylori was identified in 45 cases (50.56%) of chronic gastritis on gastric mucosal biopsies, reason behind this discrepancy may be that the chronic cases of H. pylori gastritis have low yield on biopsy and also multiple biopsies are needed for demonstration of organism.

Neoplastic stomach lesions: In the stomach, Adenocarcinoma was more common [08 cases (88.9%)] with one case (11.1%) of GIST. In our

study, concerning the differentiation of gastric carcinoma, poorly differentiated adenocarcinoma (56%) was slightly more common than moderately differentiated adenocarcinoma (44%). Kato Y et al. [19] in their study noted that there was a significant decrease in the well-differentiated carcinoma in Japan which correlated with our study.

Our study constituted three cases of signet ring cell carcinoma, all of which showed growth in the body of the stomach. Male: Female ratio was 3:1. Signet ring cell carcinomas may form lacy or delicate trabecular glandular growth and they may display a zonal or solid arrangement. Special stains (PAS, mucicarmine, or alcian blue) help to detect sparsely dispersed tumor cells in the stroma. Numerous researches have also supported this, indicating that malignant neoplasms are more common than benign ones.

The tendency to treat non-neoplastic lesions that are not cancerous and the availability of commercial fast urease test kits for Helicobacter pylori detection in our institution may be the cause of the lower percentage of non-neoplastic lesions in the current study.

The majority of patients with stomach cancer complained of loss of appetite and abdominal pain when they first arrived. 09 histologically verified cases of cancer were found to have either ulceroproductive/ nodular growth during endoscopy.

Figure 4: Gastro-intestinal stromal tumor; A: Endoscopic of gastric biopsy reveals pale red submucosal mass with an ulcer. B: Microscopic image shows a well delineated tumor tissue with spindle shaped cells arranged with bland nuclei, eosinophilic cytoplasm seen arising from the submucosa. Also seen are gastric glands on the lower end.(H & E; Low power view x100)

Duodenal biopsies:

In this study, out of 22 cases, 18 cases (78.12%) were non-neoplastic, and 04 cases (21.87%) were proved to be malignancy which is comparable with a study done by Deepa Rani et al. [20] which had 20 cases (83.34%) non-neoplastic lesions and four cases (16.66%) neoplastic lesions, out of 24 cases. Whereas in a study done by Suvarna S et al. [21, 25] cases were from duodenum which had 80% neoplastic and 20% non-neoplastic cases. A well-oriented duodenal biopsy specimen should have at least 4–5 consecutive elongated, well-distended villi from the base to the tip.

The most common diagnosis in our study was chronic nonspecific inflammation followed by chronic active duodenitis, a condition associated with acid injury with dysplastic polyp were to be diagnosed. A similar study done by Sneha Jawalkar et al. [22] showed that out of 49 cases of duodenal biopsies 85.7% cases were of chronic duodenitis, however, Santhi Kiran et al. [23] revealed lower incidence, 381 cases (9.52%) out of 719 duodenal

biopsies. In four of the histologically confirmed cases of malignancy, two cases were diagnosed as adenocarcinoma and two were reported as neuroendocrine tumors, which were either reported as a mass, or nodule or presented as mucosal thickening. This is in concordance with the findings of Prasad et al. [24] and Somani et al. [25] who reported growth and mucosal thickening as the most common endoscopic finding in malignant lesions. This study highlights the importance of histopathological examination of endoscopic biopsies for the diagnosis of upper gastrointestinal lesions. Endoscopic biopsies can not only provide valuable information concerning the non-neoplastic or neoplastic nature of lesions & the primary inflammatory patterns but also aid in identifying aetiological clues i.e., infections, medication effects (Proton pump inhibitors), or toxic ischemic effects. In this investigation, peri-ampullary cancer was found in one case, while chronic non-specific duodenitis was found in the majority of duodenal biopsies.

Figure 5: Neuroendocrine tumour -Duodenum; A: Endoscopy of duodenal lesion reveals multiple umbilicated lesions which appears congested and pale red. B: Microscopy of duodenal biopsy shows uniform tumor cells in nested and insular pattern, with salt pepper chromatin seen in the submucosa (H & E; Low power view x100)

Endoscopic and Histopathological Correlation: Overall, 96.97% agreement was found between the histological and endoscopic diagnosis.

Table 8:

Studies	Years of study	Sample size	Accuracy	Sensitivity	Specificity
Patil P et al. [27]	2	100	96.96 %	97.23 %	96.30 %
Mishra R et al. [28]	1	100	98.65 %	100%	83.08 %
Machiwala K et al. [29]	1	163	82.21 %	96.25 %	68.67 %
Present study	1	120	96.97 %	96.34 %	83.89 %

Limitations:

The limitations of this study include a retrospective single-institution study instead of a community study, which may be more representative. Also, immunohistochemistry and molecular studies could not be conducted. Endoscopic biopsy cannot assess functional diseases. It cannot detect wall thickness and luminal diameter. It is difficult to diagnose if biopsy samples are insignificant in size. Complications of endoscopic biopsy are infrequent with well-experienced endoscopic medical gastroenterologists and include perforation, laceration of major blood vessels, and mucosal bleeding.

Conclusion:

Biopsy sampling of upper gastrointestinal mucosa with diagnostic endoscopy provides useful information. Limitations in diagnostic interpretation are encountered at times due to tiny biopsy material, handling, and processing artifacts. However, multiple bits of endoscopic biopsies from abnormal-looking mucosa are recommended to establish a definitive diagnosis.

Whenever there was a disagreement, the histopathological Diagnosis served to correct a mistaken endoscopic finding. Thus concludes that endoscopy alone is incomplete without HISTOPATHOLOGICAL CORRELATION and the combination of methods provides a powerful diagnostic and prognostic tool for better patient management and follow of patients with relapse.

Abbreviations:

- GI- Gastrointestinal
- UGE- Gastrointestinal endoscopy.
- PAS - Periodic Acid Schiff stain.
- SCC-Squamous Cell Carcinoma.
- GIST-Gastrointestinal Stromal Tumour.
- NET-Neuroendocrine tumor.

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